

Old technologies support circular innovation

Old technologies, such as a centuries-old, traditional Japanese method, can support circular innovation. By charring under defined conditions, the wood surface is carbonised resulting in altered properties. This refinement method eliminates the need of chemical treatment with wood preservatives and ensures fully reusable and recyclable of wood products. Apart from this, carbonisation can achieve wonderful wooden designs that can be applied in architecture and interiors. From this practice, we learn that certain culturally distinctive techniques never get outdated and can even be re-vitalised as novel circular approaches and appropriate (pre-)treatment methods.

Regional coverage and transferability

Carbonising wood is an ancient technology from Japan. The technology itself should know no regional barriers in Europe. The combination of charring and an oil treatment eliminates the need for chemical preservation of wood. The simple process makes the technology easily transferable to board production. Similar technologies may be apparent in other regions where wood enjoys a special cultural value.

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Cascading usability of the material is enforced
- ▶ For the surface treatment no chemicals are needed so that overall purity of the product is improved and remains
- ▶ Innovative waste management operations are made possible as wood is fully reusable and recyclable
- ▶ With treatments like this, sustainability of biomass use can be improved
- ▶ Public acceptance and awareness for alternative treatment methods of wood can be achieved by façades and other visible applications